

FCS-MPC without Steady-State Error for a Grid-Connected Cascaded H-Bridge Multilevel Inverter

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Abstract— Cascade H-bridge multilevel (CHB-ML) inverters are an attractive alternative for supplying power to *ac* grids as they have high reliability and offer an acceptable quality of voltage at their output terminals. To achieve efficient operation in these CHB-ML inverters, they must work at low switching frequencies. The finite-control set model predictive control (FCS-MPC) scheme is a very intuitive strategy for controlling this type of converter, but traditional FCS-MPC algorithms generally have a steady-state error when operating at low sampling frequencies and/or if the supposed parameters of the predictive models differ from those of the real system. In this paper, a grid-connected CHB-ML inverter that uses an improved FCS-MPC scheme is proposed. The proposed strategy eliminates the steady-state error in an MPC operating at low sampling frequencies and maintains correct operation when a change in the reference of the control occurs. Experimental results from a grid-connected CHB-ML inverter with three units (seven levels) demonstrate the feasibility of the proposal.

Keywords—CHB Inverters, Multilevel Inverters, Zero Steady-State Error, FCS-MPC, Predictive Control

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the decrease in the cost of renewable energy sources has brought a significant increase in the number of projects aiming to integrate these sources with distribution networks. Inverters based on power electronics form a fundamental part of these energy integration projects, but at the same time can be their Achilles' heel, since any problem in these converters can cause a complete loss of supply from the associated sources [1]. In larger projects, when the number of energy sources increases, it is necessary to consider converters that offer more robust and resilient operation. In this way, integrating these sources with the network provides security that a failure in any element of the power electronics will not cause the operation of the system to fail [1]-[3].

To inject energy from photovoltaic panels or other *dc* sources into *ac* grids, it is possible to use cascaded H-bridge multilevel (CHB-ML) inverters. A CHB-ML inverter can allow a direct connection to a medium voltage (MV) distribution network, as suggested in [1] and shown in Fig. 1. This topology increases the reliability of the system and at the same time allows a better power quality to be achieved compared with the classic two- or three-level inverters [4]-[6]. From the point of view of reliability, these multilevel

inverters are recognised for their ability to continue operating even if one of the modules that compose the converter fails. The better power quality of these converters also allows minimisation (or eventual elimination) of the *ac* filters needed in the power output [1],[3]-[4].

Standard finite-control set model predictive control (FCS-MPC) also known as direct MPC, can be an excellent option for a control strategy in a CHB-ML inverter and for managing the power injection to a grid from multiple *dc* sources. This strategy guarantees robust operation and improved dynamic characteristics for the converter [7]-[12]. However, to achieve better efficiencies in multilevel inverters, it is necessary to operate at low switching frequencies [13]-[19]. In a standard FCS-MPC scheme, low switching frequencies can be achieved by reducing the sampling frequency in the digital signal processing (DSP) system that executes the control algorithm. A reduction in the DSP's sampling frequency and a possible mismatch (or difference) of parameters in the model in regards to the parameters of the real system will increase the steady-state error between the reference and the variable controlled by the MPC scheme. [20]-[22].

This paper considers the following hypothesis: If the proposed MPC algorithm takes into account an online correction of the error in the model (with respect to the real system) in the steady state, the control error will be zero in the steady state as a final result. Thus, the main goals of this work are to propose a new predictive scheme to control the current of a grid-connected CHB-ML inverter and to eliminate the steady-state error caused by model parameter mismatch and the low sampling frequencies of the DSP, implying that the proposed algorithm will allow operation at low switching frequencies in the converter.

II. FINITE-CONTROL SET MODEL PREDICTIVE CONTROL IN A CHB-ML INVERTER

A. Standard FCS-MPC for Current Control in a Grid-Connected ML-CHB Inverter

The purpose of a standard FCS-MPC scheme is to find a set of optimal inputs (s_{opt}) to a system such that the inputs evaluated in the system model allow minimization of an objective function J related to the control actions to be performed.

Fig.1 Example of a three-phase grid-connected ML-CHB inverter, injecting power to a distribution system

To control the current i_s (and therefore the power) of a grid-connected CHB-ML inverter using FCS-MPC, it is necessary in the first place to have the model on the grid side of the system. This model depends on a switching array or vector \mathbf{s}_h of the converter, where m vectors are valid states and can be considered viable inputs to the system. The m possible control inputs (to the inverter) must be evaluated to determine the possible grid current values. By minimizing a J function that in this case depends on the difference between the grid current i_s and its reference, an optimal input (switching vector) to apply at a discrete time $k+1$ could be found. Since the i_s current will depend on a combination of inputs \mathbf{s}_h , the optimal set of inputs \mathbf{s}_{opt} can be written as:

$$\mathbf{s}_{opt}(k+1) = \min_{h=1,2,\dots,m} J \left(\left| i_{ref}(k+1) - i_s(\mathbf{s}_h(k+1)) \right| \right) \quad (1)$$

Thus from (1), and to reinforce the previous idea, it is possible to say that to find the set of optimal inputs at a future discrete time $k+1$, m possible input combinations need to be considered, which must be evaluated in the model of the current i_s .

In this context, it is worth emphasizing that the inputs \mathbf{s}_h directly influence a switched variable of the system. In the general case of voltage source inverters (VSIs), a possible change of the input in every sample result in a switched output voltage v_o in the inverter, which also depends on the dc voltage/s. Thus, in a VSI controlled by FCS-MPC, if an optimal set of inputs \mathbf{s}_{opt} is found for a sample, an optimal output voltage v_{opt} is produced that can be represented as:

$$v_{opt} = v_o(\mathbf{s}_{opt}) \quad (2)$$

Taking this into consideration, to control the output current of a grid-connected CHB-ML inverter, employing a standard FCS-MPC scheme, the following should be considered.

B. Model of a Grid-Connected CHB-ML Inverter and its Standard FCS-MPC Strategy

Consider a single-phase grid-connected CHB-ML inverter, as shown in Fig. 2. The behaviour of the ac current i_s in this system can be described as follows:

$$\frac{di_s}{dt} = \frac{1}{L} (v_o - i_s r - v_s), \quad (3)$$

where v_s is the voltage at the point of common coupling (PCC), r and L are the resistance and the inductance at the output of the inverter respectively, and v_o is the sum of the individual voltages of each of the n_c modules that make up the inverter. This voltage v_o depends on the switching array of the converter (\mathbf{s}_h) and the dc voltage array (\mathbf{v}_{dc}) of the modules, and can be represented as:

$$v_o(\mathbf{s}_h) = \sum_{\ell=1}^{n_c} v_{dc\ell} (s_{1\ell} - s_{2\ell}) \quad (4)$$

Fig.2 Single-phase grid-connected CHB-ML inverter with n_c modules in cascade formation

Fig.3 Flowchart of standard FCS-MPC for a grid-connected CHB-ML inverter

In (4), $s_{1\ell}$ and $s_{2\ell}$ correspond to the binary signals of the switching array. These activate one of three possible levels (0, $+v_{dc}$ and $-v_{dc}$) in each of the modules.

It is also well known that the number of levels (N) in a phase of a CHB-ML inverter is:

$$N = 2n_c + 1, \quad (5)$$

where n_c is the number of modules in series. Given the 2^{2n_c} possible states of the single-phase ML-CHB inverter (without redundancies), a flowchart can be proposed for the standard FCS-MPC scheme in the inverter, as shown in Fig. 3.

Comparing the strategy shown in the flowchart in Fig. 3 with a standard FCS-MPC approach for converters [12], the one shown here differs only in the alternation algorithm block (block marked with “*”) used to ensure that each module in the cascade delivers the same power, as described in [23]. In a FCS-MPC scheme, it is essential that the mathematical modelling of the system to be controlled (block marked with “@”) gives predictions of behaviour that are as close as possible to the real response, since the more accurate the model, the smaller the error between the reference and the controlled variable.

Since a model of a system always has uncertainties, the standard MPC will always give a response with a steady-state error. This error will be smaller as the uncertainties are reduced, and conversely, a higher uncertainty in the model gives a greater steady-state error in the control for a given reference.

This paper presents a proposal that eliminates the error in the steady state for a grid-connected ML-CHB inverter controlled with an FCS-MPC scheme, even if there are significant uncertainties in the model used for the predictive strategy. However, the proposed method can be applied to any converter in which ac variables controlled through MPC. A comprehensive proposal is presented below.

III. PROPOSAL TO ELIMINATE STEADY-STATE CONTROL ERROR IN FCS-MPC APPLIED TO SINGLE-PHASE GRID-CONNECTED CONVERTERS

A. Compensating for the Steady-State Error in a Model with AC Variables

When a converter is working in the steady state, it can be represented as a linearized and discretized system around an operating point. To simplify this explanation, let us suppose there is only one relevant state in a single-phase converter. If for a discrete time $k+1$ it is possible to find an output $y(k+1)$, and if it is known that this output can be achieved through an input “ u ” that depends on the switching array of the converter in the system $u(s_h)$, for a system without uncertainties, both the states and the output can be written as:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} x(k+1) &= Ax(k) + Bu(s_h) \\ y(k+1) &= Cx(k) + Du(s_h) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

where $x(k+1)$ is the state of the system, $y(k+1)$ is the desired output at the instant $k+1$ and A , B , C and D are parameters of the linearized and discretized system. If this model is used in a predictive control scheme, and if it is assumed that the measurements (or estimations) of $x(k)$ and the parameters have no uncertainties, the prediction that can be made with the model should be exact, and without error in the steady state.

However, in practice, there will always be uncertainties, in the estimated model of a system, that are associated with the measurement (or estimation) of both the state variables and the parameters. Thus, in this work, it is assumed that this model with uncertainties can be written as:

Fig.4 General flowchart of FCS-MPC in a discrete *ac* linear system without error in the steady state

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \tilde{x}(k+1) &= \tilde{A}\tilde{x}(k) + \tilde{B}u'(k) \\ \tilde{y}(k+1) &= \tilde{C}\tilde{x}(k) + \tilde{D}u'(k) \end{aligned} \right\}, \quad (7)$$

where $\tilde{x}(k+1)$ is the predicted state of the system with uncertainties, $\tilde{x}(k)$ is the same state at the discrete instant k , $u'(k)$ is a control input, which is not necessarily equal to the input $u(s_h)$ of the system without uncertainties, and \tilde{A} , \tilde{B} , \tilde{C} , and \tilde{D} are parameters of this inaccurate discretized system. If the aim is to achieve an output precisely equal to the output produced in (6) based on the input $u'(k)$ of this system (i.e. without error in the steady state), it is known from (6) and (7) that:

$$u'(k) = \frac{Cx(k) - \tilde{C}\tilde{x}(k) + Du(s_h)}{\tilde{D}}. \quad (8)$$

That is to say, in order to control a system (in the steady-state) with FCS-MPC using a model with uncertainties and to achieve the same output as in the accurate model in Equation (6), it is necessary to use the control input of Equation (8). By replacing the input in (8) in the state equation for the model in (6), it is possible to write:

$$\tilde{x}(k+1) = \tilde{A}\tilde{x}(k) + \tilde{B} \left(\frac{Cx(k) - \tilde{C}\tilde{x}(k) + Du(s_h)}{\tilde{D}} \right) \quad (9)$$

Knowing the exact values of C , \tilde{C} , $x(k)$, $\tilde{x}(k)$, D and \tilde{D} , an inaccurate model could be found so that in the steady state, its output could produce the same desired output as in

an accurate model, but the uncertainty cannot be known, meaning that the difference $Cx(k) - \tilde{C}\tilde{x}(k)$ is apparently impossible to find. However, it can be assumed that this difference $Cx(k) - \tilde{C}\tilde{x}(k)$ is proportional to the effect of the error $e(k)$ on the desired output of the system. If the desired output in an *ac* system in the steady state is represented in discrete time and using a sampling time T_s , it can be written as:

$$y^*(k) = \hat{y} \cdot \cos(\omega_0 k T_s). \quad (10)$$

It is then possible to define the effect of the error on the desired output of the system through a convolution, i.e.:

$$u_{y^*e}(k) = \hat{y} \cdot \cos(\omega_0 k T_s) * e(k). \quad (11)$$

Assuming that

$$(Cx(k) - \tilde{C}\tilde{x}(k)) \approx \alpha u_{y^*e}, \quad (12)$$

then from (8), (11) and (12), the input $u'(k)$ can be represented as:

$$u'(k) = \frac{\alpha \cdot \hat{y} \cdot \cos(\omega_0 k T_s) * e(k) + Du(s_h)}{\tilde{D}}. \quad (13)$$

Since in FCS-MPC the error is evaluated at every iteration, this error can be used to find the new input $u'(k)$. By transforming the control input $u'(k)$ in (13) to the discrete z -plane, it can be written as:

$$u'(z) = \frac{\alpha \hat{y}}{\tilde{D}} res_{(\omega_0)} \{y^*(z) - \tilde{y}(z)\} + \frac{D}{\tilde{D}} u(s_h). \quad (14)$$

Here, $res_{(\omega_0)}$ corresponds to

$$res_{(\omega_0)} = \left(\frac{1 - z^{-1} \cos(\omega_0 T_s)}{1 - 2z^{-1} \cos(\omega_0 T_s) + z^{-2}} \right) \quad (15)$$

which is a resonance that can be applied to the difference (the error) between the reference and the output of the system, and the term $u(s_h)$ can correspond to a standard input in an FCS-MPC. Since one can assume a smaller difference between D and \tilde{D} , the input $u'(z)$ that is used online to correct the inaccurate model could be simplified and rewritten as:

$$u'(z) \approx \underbrace{K \cdot res_{(\omega_0)} \{y^*(z) - \tilde{y}(z)\}}_{u_{cmp}} + \underbrace{u(s_h)}_{to\ optimize}, \quad (16)$$

where K is a real number that can take positive or negative values, and which can be adjusted. It is important to note that $u'(z)$ can be separated into two terms: a compensation term u_{cmp} and an optimization term that can be found directly through the MPC strategy. Fig. 4 shows a flowchart for a direct predictive control scheme based on a linearized model with uncertainties, but in which the error is guaranteed to be zero in the steady state.

Since Equations (6) and (7) correspond to linearized discrete models (exact and uncertain models, respectively) of any converter with a relevant variable operating in the steady state, it is valid to infer that the compensation input u_{cmp} , which reduces to zero the error of the linearized steady-state model, can be applied in a model that is not necessarily linearized. In other words, if the new input can eliminate the error in the steady state for an inaccurate linearized discrete model, it can also compensate the original discrete uncertain model.

IV. ELIMINATING THE STEADY-STATE ERROR IN MODEL OF AN FCS-MPC APPLIED TO A GRID-CONNECTED CHB-ML INVERTER

When applying the theoretical development considered above in FCS-MPC to control the ac current i_s of a grid-connected CHB-ML inverter, the following steps should be carried out.

A prediction horizon of one for the current i_s should be used. Since the discrete model of the current has uncertainties, from (3) it can be written that

$$\tilde{i}_s(k+1) = \frac{T_s}{\tilde{L}} (v'_o - \tilde{r} \tilde{i}_s(k) - \tilde{v}_s(k)) + \tilde{i}_s(k), \quad (17)$$

where $\tilde{i}_s(k+1)$ is the uncertain current prediction at the instant $k+1$, T_s is the sampling period, v'_o is the ac voltage of the inverter in the model that can be used as input in the MPC, \tilde{L} is the uncertain value of the inductance, \tilde{r} is the uncertain value of the resistance in the line, $\tilde{i}_s(k)$ is the

measured current of the line (which may also contain uncertainty), and $\tilde{v}_s(k)$ is the grid voltage measured at the connection point. It is clear that since it contains uncertainties, the model cannot predict the currents needed to achieve zero steady-state error in FCS-MPC.

The control input to the system with uncertainties is the voltage v'_o in the model (equivalent to $u'(k)$ in the previous chapter). When using Equation (16) to achieve zero steady-state error in an MPC, the term v'_o in (17) could be replaced by the sum of the inverter voltage found by standard FCS-MPC and a compensation voltage, i.e.

$$v'_o = v_o + v_{cmp}, \quad (18)$$

where the compensation voltage v_{cmp} corresponds to the resonance of the error between the reference and output current. Assuming that the error used for FCS-MPC is the estimated error, and representing the compensation term v_{cmp} in the discrete z -plane, it can be written:

$$v_{cmp}(z) \approx K \frac{1 - z^{-1} \cos(\omega_0 T_s)}{1 - 2z^{-1} \cos(\omega_0 T_s) + z^{-2}} e_e(z) \quad (19)$$

where $e_e(z)$ is the estimation error between the reference and output current in FCS-MPC. To simplify the presentation of this compensation term in the flowchart, it can be written as follows:

$$v_{cmp}(z) = K \cdot res_{(\omega_0)} \{i_{ref}(z) - \tilde{i}_s(z)\}. \quad (20)$$

The model that can be evaluated in the control scheme of a grid-connected CHB-ML inverter, and which achieves zero steady-state error, can be presented as:

$$\tilde{i}_s(k+1) = \frac{T_s}{\tilde{L}} \left(\underbrace{(v_o(s_h) + v_{cmp})}_{v'_o} - \tilde{r} \tilde{i}_s(k) - \tilde{v}_s(k) \right) + \tilde{i}_s(k) \quad (21)$$

Fig. 5 shows a flowchart for the proposed scheme, in which FCS-MPC is implemented to control the ac current in an grid-connected ML-CHB inverter without error in the steady state. As can be seen from this flowchart, the strategy corresponds to a direct predictive control scheme in which only one input compensation term, v_{cmp} , is added to the model to eliminate the steady-state error. This term is calculated from the resonance of the error between the reference and the current measurement.

The gain K can be adjusted quickly; however, it is essential to mention that a large gain K will produce overshoot against a step input in the reference, while a low value of K will lead to zero error in the steady state but in a slower way. This paper does not propose an analytical method for adjusting this gain; however, an adjustment based

Fig.5 General flowchart for an implementation of the proposed MPC in a grid-connected CHB-ML inverter

on trial and error can be carried out if there is support from numerical simulations before implementing the system.

Finally, it should be emphasized that direct MPC strategies can achieve a minimal steady-state error if the sampling frequency is high. However, at higher sampling rates, the switching frequencies increase, giving higher switching losses. By reducing the sampling frequency, the uncertainties in a model of a traditional MPC direct strategy increase, thus increasing the steady-state error. Our proposal allows the sampling frequency to be reduced, which in turn

reduces the switching frequency, but also achieves zero error in the steady state. This latter is very desirable in multilevel converters.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To verify the hypothesis proposed in this paper, a seven-level grid-connected CHB-ML inverter prototype (with three H-bridge modules) was built and experimental results were obtained using this prototype. For security, the converter was connected to the low-voltage side of a grid-connected

Fig.6 General scheme of the implemented system

Fig.7 Systems used for the experimental tests.

transformer, as shown in Fig. 6. The control scheme in Fig. 6 was implemented using a dSPACE MicrolabBox. Fig. 7 illustrates the scheme and the parts of the implemented system. System data and parameters are presented in Table I. It can be seen from the table that in the model (for the FCS-MPC scheme implemented), different parameter values are considered with respect to the real parameters of the system, including a 20% error in the line inductance parameter and 83% in the line resistance. This difference was generated deliberately, in order to highlight the steady-state error in the standard FCS-MPC due to uncertainties in the model. The results obtained in these experiments enable a comparison of

TABLE I. DATA AND REAL PARAMETERS VERSUS THOSE USED IN THE MPC

Parameters or data	Tag	Value in MPC (A)	Real value (B)
Line resistance	r	0.1 Ω	0.6 Ω
Line inductance	L	20 mH	25 mH
dc voltage HB1	V_{dc1}	30 V	
dc voltage HB2	V_{dc2}	30 V	
dc voltage HB3	V_{dc3}	30 V	
Voltage at connection point	V_s	63 V	
Sampling frequency-ex.1	f_s	20 kHz	
Sampling frequency-ex.2	f_s	10 kHz	
Sampling frequency-ex.3	f_s^*	5 kHz	

*This sampling frequency was used for all experiments from the third onward

the operation of the grid-connected converter between a standard FCS-MPC strategy and the proposed MPC strategy.

A. Steady-State Operation in a Standard FCS-MPC Using Different Sample Rates in the Control System

First, a standard FCS-MPC strategy was used to control the ac current of the grid-connected converter and carried out three tests in the steady state. In these tests, three different sampling frequencies were considered for the MPC implemented in the system. In the first test, a sampling frequency of 20 kHz was used. From the results acquired

Fig.8 Steady-state waveforms and harmonic spectra for the system using standard MPC, working at a sample rate of 20 kHz; (a) output voltages of the H-Bridges, (b) multilevel output voltage, (c) reference, ac current and error, (d) spectrum of v_{o1} (e) spectrum of v_o (f) spectrum of i_s .

Fig.9 Steady-state waveforms and harmonic spectra for the system using standard MPC, working at a sample rate of 10 kHz; (a) output voltages of the H-Bridges, (b) multilevel output voltage, (c) reference, ac current and error, (d) spectrum of v_{o1} (e) spectrum of v_o (f) spectrum of i_s .

with the oscilloscope shown in Fig. 8, it is possible to see the three voltages for each of the H-bridges (v_{o1} , v_{o2} , and v_{o3}), and in the same figure, the waveform of the total voltage (v_o) can be seen. In the lower part of Fig. 8, the current injected by the converter can be seen with its reference, and finally, the control error in the steady state. The error acquired by the oscilloscope is obtained through a digital/analog channel (DAC) of the dSPACE. The same is done for the current reference. From Fig. 8, it can be seen that the error is barely noticeable due to a fundamental frequency oscillation. The error exists mainly due to the difference between the real parameters of the system and those used in the model of the MPC strategy.

In the second experiment, the system was again

implemented with a traditional FCS-MPC strategy, but 10 kHz was used as the sampling frequency. Fig. 9 clearly shows that in this experiment, the number of commutations decreases, both in the individual voltages of each H-bridge and in the total voltage of the converter. In the lower part of the oscilloscope acquisition (Fig. 9), it is possible to appreciate that there is a slightly higher difference between the reference and the current that is tried to control. This can also be seen by comparing the error obtained by the DAC in Fig. 9 with the error obtained in Fig. 8 for a system operating at a sampling rate of 20 kHz (in the first experiment).

In the third test, also carried out in the steady state, the waveforms were obtained using standard FCS-MPC but at a

Fig.10 Steady-state waveforms and harmonic spectra for the system using standard MPC, working at a sample rate of 5 kHz; (a) output voltages of the H-Bridges, (b) multilevel output voltage, (c) reference, ac current and error, (d) spectrum of v_{o1} (e) spectrum of v_o (f) spectrum of i_s .

Fig.11 Waveforms of the system when changing from a standard FCS-MPC to the proposed MPC (a) output voltages of the H-Bridges, (b) multilevel output voltage, (c) reference, ac current and error,

Fig.12 Steady-state waveforms and harmonic spectra for the system when using the proposed MPC, working at a sample rate of 5 kHz; (a) output voltages of the H-Bridges, (b) multilevel output voltage, (c) reference, ac current and error, (d) spectrum of v_{o1} (e) spectrum of v_o (f) spectrum of i_s .

sampling rate of 5kHz. Fig. 10 presents the results of this test, and clearly shows a lower number of commutations for each H-bridge. This fact becomes more evident when the inverter voltage waveforms are compared with the first test waveforms obtained at a sample rate of 20 kHz (shown in Fig. 8). Unfortunately, an increase in the steady-state error is evident in this case, both when observing the reference with respect to the controlled current and the error oscillation obtained through the DAC. The harmonic distortion of these three cases could be compared in terms of the total harmonic distortion (THD) for (a) the voltage of each module; (b) the THD for the total output voltage; and (c) the THD for the output current of the inverter. The lower distortion at higher sampling rates is mainly due to the spread spectrum concentrated at higher frequencies and the better tracking achieved in terms of control (of the current). However, a higher switching frequency is not desirable in these inverters, since this leads to higher switching losses.

B. Changing from a Standard FCS-MPC to the Proposed MPC

The fourth experiment involved the application of the proposed MPC at $t = 0$ s. As can be seen from Fig. 11, the system initially operates with a standard FCS-MPC strategy. That is, in the control scheme shown in Fig. 6, the user applies the c bit (from 0 to 1) at $t = 0$. The control scheme then changes from a standard FCS-MPC strategy to the proposed MPC, working in both approaches with a sample

rate of the dSPACE of just 5 kHz. It is possible to see that the error in the steady-state starts to be eliminated from $t = 0$ onwards. From Fig. 11, it can be seen that the control minimizes the error in almost half a cycle.

C. Steady-State Operation with Proposed MPC

Fig. 12 shows the operation of the proposed MPC in the system in the steady state, operating at a sample rate of 5 kHz in the dSPACE. This figure shows the output voltages of each module, the multilevel output of the converter, the reference with the controlled current, and the error obtained through DAC. In addition, it is observable that the error has a small ripple, due to the inverter switching. On the other hand, as can be seen from Fig. 12(b), the concentration of the voltage spectrum of each module (mainly) has values less than 5 kHz, due to the sampling frequency used in the MPC scheme. In the same way, it can be noted that the harmonics of the total voltage are concentrated in values of less than 5 kHz (around 2.5 kHz). However, the magnitudes of the harmonics are up to three times lower with respect to the individual voltages of each module. This is expected behaviour for the ML-CHB inverter. Finally, the THD of the output voltages in each H-bridge is 54.6%, while the THD of the total output voltage is 17.4%. The small improvement in the THD of the current in the proposed MPC (without error), regarding the standard MPC strategy, is due to the better tracking achieved with the proposed scheme. A

Fig.13 Waveforms of the dynamic response of the system when using a standard FCS-MPC working at a sample rate of 5kHz, showing the step response from 1.5 to 3 A in the reference; (a) ac voltage at the connection point (b) multilevel output voltage (c) reference, output current and error.

Fig.14 Waveforms of the dynamic response of the system when using the proposed MPC working at a sample rate of 5 kHz, showing the step response from 1.5 to 3 A in the reference; (a) ac voltage at the connection point (b) multilevel output voltage (c) reference, output current and error.

normalized root-mean-square measure of the control error (*NRMSE*) can be used to compare the performance of the MPC schemes regarding the steady-state error. The *NRMSE* is defined as:

$$NRMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T (i_{ref} - i_s)^2 dt}}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \int_0^T i_{ref}^2 dt}}. \quad (22)$$

Table II provides a summary with the most relevant results of the tests performed in steady-state.

From these results, it is good to note that the proposed MPC scheme achieves almost the same value in the index *NRMSE* that for a standard FCS-MPC strategy operating at a sampling frequency of 20kHz.

D. Dynamic Response Comparison

Finally, two tests are performed on the converter to compare the control systems against step-changes in the current reference: the first test operates with the standard FCS-MPC strategy, and the second with the proposed MPC scheme. Fig. 13 shows the operation of the converter with a traditional FCS-MPC. From this figure, the voltage (v_s) at the point where the converter is connected, the total output voltage of the multilevel inverter, the current injected into the grid together with its reference and the error between the controlled current and reference can be observed. It is possible to observe that before and after the change in the reference, at $t = 0$ s of the acquisition, there is a considerable error in the current control. It can also be seen that the higher the current, the more significant the error, since with higher current levels the differences in the uncertainties between the model and the real system become more evident.

Finally, when performing the last experimental test, using the proposed MPC strategy (for reducing the steady-state error to zero), it is possible to see in Fig. 14, the same variables observed in the previous test (Fig. 13), and where the system undergoes the same change in the reference. The most notable difference is that in the steady state, the proposed scheme has an error of practically zero before the abrupt change in the reference at $t = 0$ s. Once the change in the reference has occurred, the control system takes the *ac* current i_s as close as possible to the setpoint signal; the dynamics in this last test match the dynamics of the previous test. It is noteworthy that the value of the filter inductance

limits the observed dynamics of the current. Lastly, it can be seen that the error increases at the moment of change, as in the case of a standard FCS-MPC; however, the error is quickly reduced to values around zero.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The standard FCS-MPC scheme is a very intuitive strategy that can be used to control practically any converter. However, if the model used in the scheme contains uncertainties, the MPC approach will have a prediction error, and as a result, will have a steady-state mismatch between the measured and desired output. In this paper, it is shown that the uncertainties in an *ac* model can be reduced to zero for an MPC used in the control of a single-phase grid-connected ML-CHB inverter.

The theoretical proposal indicates that if the *ac* output voltage in the MPC model is replaced by the sum of the predictive optimization, plus a resonance between the reference and the variable to be controlled, it is possible to reduce the model error to zero in the steady-state. Thus, this would eliminate the steady-state mismatch between the measured and desired output. The experimental results showed that decreasing the sampling frequency decreases the switching frequency but increases the control error (as the uncertainties increase) in a standard FCS-MPC. The same experimental results demonstrated that, through the proposal, it is possible to reduce the sampling rate of the control system and operate without error in the steady-state with an MPC applied to a grid-connected CHB-ML inverter.

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TABLE II -EXPERIMENTAL TEST RESULTS IN STEADY STATE

Sample Frequency	MPC Type	<i>NRMSE</i> in S.S.	Output Current THD	Output Voltage THD
20kHz	<i>Standard FCS-MPC</i>	0.0406 p.u.	0.0114 p.u	0.0582 p.u
10kHz	<i>Standard FCS-MPC</i>	0.0815 p.u.	0.0144 p.u.	0.0928 p.u
5kHz	<i>Standard FCS-MPC</i>	0.1686 p.u.	0.0203 p.u.	0.1735 p.u.
5kHz	<i>Proposed MPC</i>	0.0459 p.u.	0.0194 p.u.	0.1744 p.u.

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